

Effectiveness of Regenerative Agriculture Technologies in Sustainable Farming Systems of Imo state Nigeria

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Abstract: The study evaluated Effectiveness of regenerative agricultural technologies in sustainable farming systems of Imo state Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to: examine demographic factors affecting adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies, identify regenerative agriculture technologies adopted in the study area, identify motivator variables required by farmers to increase adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies and evaluate the association between factors affecting adoption of regenerative agriculture and adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies. Structured questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection and administered to 350 respondents. Multivariate Probit Model (MVP) and percentages were used to analyse the data. The findings of the study indicates that several demographic factors including performance of adopted technologies (89%), land availability (75.6%), availability of good varieties (70%), knowledge on regenerative agriculture(60%), availability of water (40.5%), labour intensity(35%), landscape(33.3%) and cultural practices (20%) affect adoption of regenerative agriculture. Regenerative agriculture technologies adopted include crop rotation (96%), mixed farming (88.8%), mulching (76.3%), early maturing varieties (75.5%), cereal legume intercropping (71.3%), pasture cropping (72%), water storage in ponds (69%) and drip irrigation (50.4%). Motivator variables required by farmers to increase adoption of regenerative agriculture include input subsidy (87.6%), on – farm experiment (80.3%), credit provision (52.8%), extension visits (45%), storage system (68%) and enhanced market outlet (84.5%). Government and other agricultural policy makers should take these factors into consideration while making decisions and formulating policies to support the dissemination and adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies.

Keywords: Effectiveness, regenerative agriculture technologies, sustainable farming systems

Introduction

Regenerative agriculture is a transformative approach to shift from conventional farming practices to sustainable and organic farming approaches. The essence is to restore soil health, ameliorate the effect of climatic change and enhance biodiversity. The key principles are to stabilize soil structure through a diverse crop rotation system, use of cover crops and integration of livestock grazing (Ahmad, 2023). Regenerative agriculture as a farming approach prioritizes soil conservation as the entry point to regenerate and promote multiple positioning through regulating projecting ecosystem services to achieve food and environmental sustainability (Schreefel et al., 2020).

In Imo state, agricultural practice is characterised by subsistence agriculture due to practice of land tenure system. The land tenure system leads to fragmentation of individual farm lands, restricting mechanisation for farm operations. There is still need to meet the increasing demand for land productivity, it necessitates incorporation of new production systems that will open up new lands for cultivation by transforming new lands through cultivation patterns. Cultivation patterns are prone to the challenges of land deterioration, declining productivity as well as extreme weather stress (Kiboi *et al.*, 2019; Ndeke *et al.*, 2021). These challenges make it

necessary to transform agricultural production systems through adoption of new technologies like regenerative agriculture technologies (Gosnell *et al.*, 2019).

Adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies is important because the impacts and challenges of climate change are becoming increasingly evident throughout Nigeria. This is conspicuous as drought, flooding, rains, significant soil erosion, high input prices and fluctuating fuel prices result in small holder farmers shifting from low productivity and profitability. The situation is aggravated with production constraints like poor output per hectare, resilience to change, poor access to mechanization, lack of technology, poor agronomic practices, management of soil and water resources and poor access to finance (Centre for Dry land Agriculture, 2020).

There are five principles that guide regenerative agriculture approach namely: minimizing soil disturbance, keeping the soil covered all year round, keeping live plants and roots in the soil for as long as possible, incorporating biodiversity and integration of animals (Khangura *et al.*, 2023). These principles help to achieve the dividends of diverse farming systems like multiple ecosystem services. The principles gave rise to three models: diffusion of innovation model, perception of adoption model and economic constraint model so as

to explain forces that influence adoption of regenerative agriculture technology. Hence, this research analysed factors affecting adoption of regenerative technologies, motivator variables that increase adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies and regenerative agriculture technologies adopted farmers.

Materials and Method

The study was conducted in Imo state which is located within latitudes 4° 45'N and 7° 15'N and longitude 6° 50' and 7° 25' E in the Southeast geo – political zone of Nigeria. The state has three agricultural zones namely Owerri zone, Orlu zone and Okigwe zone. The state comprises of 27 Local Government Areas with high agricultural activities. It is characterised by bimodal rains occurring March to July and September to October. It has considerable large population of 5,459,300 with 50.3% females and 49.7% males (Brinkhoff, 2022). The study target is farmers across the geo – political zones of Imo state. List of 3500 innovative farmers was obtained from Agricultural Development Programme headquarters in Owerri. Proportionate random sampling technique was used to select 350 respondents used for the study. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data. Due to multiple responses percentages was used to analyse the information. A Multivariate Pobot Model (MVP) was used

to examine demographic factors affecting adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies.

The model was preferred because factors influencing adoption of various regenerative agriculture technologies could be correlated. MVP effects simultaneous regression of binary equations that are correlated against a single vector of predictor variables (Okello *et al.*, 2020). The model can be empirically specified as: $Y_{ia} = X_{ia}\beta + \epsilon_{ia}$

Where Y are demographic factors influencing adoption of technologies, i is the farmers' identification number. Y = 1 if demographic factor influence adoption of a technology and 0 if otherwise. X are the vectors of regenerative agriculture technologies, 1 if adopted and 0 if otherwise. a = variables 1 – 8, $\beta = \beta_1 - \beta_8$ (vectors of unknown parameters) and $\epsilon_i =$ disturbance term.

Results and Discussion

The results in Table 1 show that performance of adopted technologies (89.0%), land availability (75.6%), availability of good varieties (70.0%), knowledge on regenerative agriculture (60.0%), availability of water (40.5%), labour intensity (35.0%), landscape (33.3%) and cultural practices (20.0%) were the factors affecting adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies in Imo state. The

findings is in tandem with those of Chan *et al.*, 2018 who observed that sticking to traditional methods, awareness and poor professional knowledge on particular innovation, weather and performance uncertainties were the common factors hindering adoption of regenerative

agriculture technologies among farmers in developing countries. Senyelo *et al.*, (2018) observed that weed management makes regenerative agriculture labour intensive and farmers are likely to avoid adoption due to high production costs.

Table 1: Demographic factors

Factors	Percentages
Performance of adopted technology	89.0
Land availability	75.6
Availability of good varieties	70.0
Knowledge on regenerative agriculture	60.0
Availability of water	40.5
Labour intensity	35.0
Landscape	33.3
Cultural practices	20.0

Source: Field survey, 2022

The main regenerative agriculture technologies used by farmers in Imo state are captured in Table 2. The results show the sequence of prioritization of regenerative agriculture technologies by farmers. It shows that most adopted regenerative agricultural technologies as crop rotation (96%), mixed farming (88.8%), mulching (76.3%), early maturing varieties

(75.5%), pasture cropping (72.0%), cereal legume intercropping (71.3%), water storage in ponds and use of drip irrigation (50.4%). The findings are consistent with those by UNDP Nigeria (2022) that Nigeria farmers adopt regenerative agriculture which strengthens them against extreme climatic and environmental conditions.

Table 2: Regenerative agriculture technologies

Technologies	Percentages
Crop rotation	96.0
Mixed farming	88.8
Mulching	76.3
Early maturing varieties	75.5
Pasture cropping	72.0
Cereal legume intercropping	71.3
Water storage in ponds	69.0
Use of drip irrigation	50.4

Source: Field survey, 2022

Results on Table 3 shows that 87.6% of the respondents would need input subsidy to enhance their adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies. 84.5% would need enhance market outlet for their products. 80.3% would need on - farm experiments by extension agents to ascertain the thrive ability of the technology. 68.0% would need to be provided with durable storage system, 52.8% would need to be provided with credits to enhance their purchasing power

while 45.5% would need routine visits from extension agents to monitor the implementation program of the technologies to ensure clarity. These results concur with the findings of Beke (2020) who found that land, finance, seed production, tax and water pose significant challenges for agricultural businesses in Nigeria so there is need for government to make investment promotion policies.

Table 3: Motivating variables for the adoption of regenerative agricultural technologies by the farmers

Motivating variables	Percentages
Input subsidy	87.6
Enhanced market outlet	84.5
On-farm experiment	80.3
Storage system	68.0
Credit provision	52.8
Extension visits	45.5

Source: Field survey, 2022

Results on Table 4 illustrate that availability of water significantly influenced adoption of water storage in ponds, early maturing varieties, cereal legume intercropping, pasture cropping and drip irrigation. The result concurs with Landford and Orr (2022) findings that water availability affect irrigation management, vegetative growth, resilience to drought, higher soil organic matter content and biological fertility. This is because water helps soil regenerative activities to improve physical soil fertility. It was observed that landscape diversity significantly influenced adoption of water storage in ponds, mixed farming and cereal legume intercrop. The result is in affiliation with Soils for Life (2019) report that irrespective of adoption of good agriculture, regenerative technologies decreases acidification, erosion, salinity, high evaporation and run off hence crop resilience to impacts of drought, flood and fire.

Cultural practices were found to have significant influence on adoption of crop rotation, early maturing varieties and drip irrigation. This is supported by Khanma *et al.*, (2023) findings that cultural practices which is characterised by minimum tillage is reflected through crop rotations, multi species and improved soil moisture through natural processes. This is attainable because minimum tillage increases carbon sequestration thereby reducing the

consequences of global warming. Labour intensity significantly influenced the adoption of water storage in ponds and pasture cropping. The result agrees with Day & Creamer (2022) findings that farmers face much difficulty due to low traction.

Availability of good variety significantly influenced adoption of crop rotation, mixed farming, mulching and pasture cropping. The result resonate with Day & Creamer (2022) findings that choice of new varieties are backed with government support, market availability and social acceptance. These variables must interact before they can be available to the farmer to improve regenerative agriculture.

Adopted technologies performance significantly influenced the adoption of water storage in ponds, crop rotation, mulching and cereal legume intercrop. This is based on how farmers perceive a regenerative technology. Farmers will always opt out of technologies with low return to investment. The implication is that water storage in ponds, crop rotation, mulching and cereal legume intercrop have proved to increase yield over time and this increased their adoption. Hence, technologies performance increases the likelihood of taking up agricultural innovations (Zakaria *et al.*, 2020).

Knowledge on regenerative agriculture significantly influenced the adoption of mixed farming and cereal legume inter crop.

The result is in tandem with Wilson *et al.*, (2023) study that advised that, to reap the benefit of regenerative agriculture, farmers must know how to effectively incorporate them into their overall farm management framework.

Land availability significantly influenced the adoption of mulching, early maturing

varieties and cereal legume intercrop. The result is in line with Wilson *et al.*, (2023) findings that land access is a challenge to farmers as most are quite interested in using regenerative agriculture technologies but struggle to find land to launch their operations.

Table 4: Demographic factors influencing the adoption of regenerative agriculture technologies

Variable	Water storage in ponds	Crop rotation	Mixed farming	Mulching	Early maturing varieties	Cereal legume intercropping	Pasture cropping	Drip irrigation	
	Coeff	Coeff	Coeff	Coeff	Coeff	Coeff	Coeff	Coeff	
	Std error	Std error	Std error	Std error	Std error	Std error	Std error	Std error	
Availability Of water	0.413 (0.118)***	0.112 (0.116)	-0.088 (0.119)	0.054 (0.049)	0.272 (0.115)**	0.576 (0.148)***	0.907 (0.324)***	0.232 (0.121)***	
Landscape	0.030 (0.137)	0.159 (0.127)	0.397 (0.177)***	-0.046 (0.122)	0.024 (0.231)	0.387 (0.157)***	-0.043 (0.108)	0.098 (0.123)	
Cultural practices	0.149 (0.109)	0.024 (0.099)**	-0.222 (0.148)	-0.006 (0.201)	-0.024 (0.099)**	0.038 (0.178)	0.205 (0.266)	0.278 (0.118)**	
Labour intensity	0.101 (0.094)**	0.033 (0.070)	-0.186 (0.142)	0.023 (0.079)	0.124 (0.077)	0.110 (0.172)	0.295 (0.152)**	-0.041 (0.102)	
Good variety	-0.041 (0.038)	-0.243 (0.092)***	-0.905 (0.326)***	-0.210 (0.180)	0.173 (0.327)	-0.025 (0.199)	-0.040 (0.171)	0.196 (0.205)	
Technology	-0.413 (0.118)***	0.535 (0.128)***	-0.086 (0.119)	-0.516 (0.148)***	0.035 (0.135)	-0.362 (0.112)***	0.094 (0.195)	-0.212 (0.148)	
Performance	0.022 (0.189)	0.098 (0.123)	0.272 (0.115)**	0.206 (0.276)	-0.008 (0.200)	0.907 (0.324)***	-0.094 (0.093)	0.038 (0.178)	
Regenerative agric knowledge	-0.188 (0.143)	0.198 (0.207)	0.094 (0.108)	-0.120 (0.037)***	0.213 (0.108)**	0.285 (0.150)**	0.108 (0.102)	0.063 (0.058)	
Land availability	0.584 (0.501)	1.614 (0.535)	0.521 (0.960)	-0.220 (0.559)	-1.861 (0.552)***	1.046 (0.440)	0.373 (0.536)	1.518 (0.529)	
Constant	Likelihood ratio test of Rho(ia) = 0, chi2(8) = 118.840, Prob > chi2 = 0.0000, Wald chi2(64) = 152.22 log likelihood = -910.7355, number of observations = 350								
*** and ** show significance at 1% and 5% level respectively									

Source: Field survey, 2022

Conclusion

Availability of water, landscape diversity, cultural practices, labour intensity, availability of good variety, adopted technology performance, knowledge on regenerative agriculture and landscape availability were vital determinants of adoption of regenerative agriculture by farmers. The need arises to invest in motivation approaches to encourage farmers to use regenerative agriculture on their farms to scale up productivity. The state government, NGOs and other investors should intensify regenerative agriculture updates to farmers to keep them abreast of latest innovations. Farmers should be equipped with skills to increase effectiveness in adoption of regenerative agriculture to achieve sustainable farming in Imo state.

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